

TUPROQKALA IS A FOUNDATION OF OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

This thesis is about the establishment of Tuproqkala district. The establishment of a new district in a remote village of Khorezm region was a great impetus to pay more attention to the villagers. Especially for the youth of the district, the doors of more opportunities have been opened. The responsible employees of the district and the departments controlled by the district administration and the employees responsible for youth are commendable for their selfless approach to their profession and taking responsibility deeply. Many educational centers have been opened for the purpose of meaningful spending of free time of young people. Great attention was paid to youth entrepreneurship to ensure youth employment.

Introduction. The name of Tuproqkala district is related to the name of Tuproqkala fortresses in Khorezm. In Khorezm oasis, 7 castles are called Tuproqkala. In the territory of the district there are ruins of a fortress called Tuproqkala. The castle belongs to IV-III centuries BC. The meaning of the word Tuproqkala means a building, a fortress, walled from a mixture of soil and water.

On March 23, 2020, at the next meeting of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of deputies raised the issue of changing the borders of Hazorasp district within the Khorezm region and, accordingly, establishing Tuproqkala district. Deputies noted that the creation of a new district will have a positive effect on the development of agriculture, especially cattle breeding, on the socio-economic development of the region, and on ensuring the employment of the population.

The date of establishment is March 24, 2020.

Its area is 1,60,000 square kilometers.

Hazorasp District, Bukhara Region borders the Republics of Karakalpakstan and Turkmenistan.

Population - 59,304 people (average)

The number of community assemblies is 18

Number of apartments - 14, 2 thousand. The number of families is 14,7 thousand.

National composition: Uzbeks - 55707, Turkmen - 658, Kazakhs - 229, Russians - 602, representatives of other nationalities - 2108.

The economy of the district specializes in animal husbandry, mechanical engineering, food industry, textile and textile industry, building materials production.

Neighborhoods: After Tuproqkala settlement and Pitnak city of Hazorasp district were separated and Tuproqkala district was established, the following 15 neighborhoods were added to the new district.

Places in the territory of the city of Pitnak:

1. Sakhovat
2. Muhabbat
3. Navbahor
4. Obod
5. Yuldash Okhunbobayev
6. Pastom
7. Saidlar
8. Sayopir
9. Yoshlik
10. Sharlauq
11. Sheikhs.

Villages in Tuproqkala area:

1. Hazorasp
2. The place of Nukus
3. Sarimoy
4. Tupoqkala settlement.

On the eve of the 30th anniversary of our independence, a new district was established in the Khorezm region on the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, and many changes were made for our youth, a lot of attention was paid to our district, the work of entrepreneurs was appreciated, and many doors of opportunity were opened to them, and young people He was attracted to clubs in order to spend his time meaningfully.

We young people can boldly say that the great attention paid to our youth by our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's decision to establish one district in the Khorezm region served as a golden key for the residents of remote villages and their youth. The efforts of the governor of our

district and the responsible approach of all the responsible employees in the district to their profession and position, the fact that they deal with young people separately, study the opinions of each of us, pay great attention to young people, and create all the conditions for every Dealing with one young person gives us a great uplifting spirit and gives a great impetus to further increase our love and loyalty to the Motherland.

The responsible employees of all offices and organizations in the district have kept young people busy with many sports activities, traveling classes and clubs of various subjects so that young people can spend their time meaningfully and usefully.

It is no exaggeration to say that opportunities for young people in our country are increasing year by year.

For example, no matter which network, which direction, all conditions are present. In general, there are opportunities in all sectors, whether it is studying IT, foreign languages. What is required of us young people is that we should use these opportunities wisely and contribute to the development of the country in the future. Such opportunities have opened many doors of opportunity for the youth of our district. Regardless of family status and financial situation, every young person's opinion is heard and all conditions are created for studying. In particular, interest-free and low-interest loans are allocated in large quantities to support youth entrepreneurship.

Today, young people who need social protection and have financial problems in our district are registered in the "Youth Register", and children from low-income families are listed in the "Iron Register" by the initiative of our president and the responsible employees of the district. many opportunities are being created for winter and work.

Such incentives give great enthusiasm to us young people and help us take bold steps towards our goals. It gives us young people an upbeat spirit to love the Motherland. Of course, it is necessary to use these opportunities wisely, to contribute to the prosperity and development of our country. After all, every person should contribute to this country, to the prosperity of his country.

Tuproqkala district has become a large economic zone, many unemployed residents have been provided with jobs. Many plants and factories are operating today.

Based on preliminary data, 9458.5 billion will be spent by industrial enterprises operating in the district in January-December 2022. production of industrial products amounted to 114.3% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year. 7566.6 billion in the reporting year. Soum consumer goods were produced and made 127.9 percent compared to January-December 2022. In particular, 2092.4 billion soums worth of food and 5474.2 billion soums of non-food products were produced, with a growth rate of 121.4 percent and 130, respectively, compared to January-December 2022. 6 percent, and its share in the total production of consumer goods was 27.7 percent and 72.3 percent.

Contribution of small business in industrial production. Today, small business and private entrepreneurship provide the domestic market of our country with goods and services, increase employment and real incomes of the population, rational distribution of resources and

their effective use, reduce the disparity of incomes of social groups, and improve mutual relations between different sectors of the economy. is of great importance and is the main catalyst for deepening reforms. Small business and private business entities are able to quickly adapt to changes in market conditions and changes in consumer demand, and play an important role in maintaining balance in the consumer market. It also serves to create a competitive environment. 9458.5 billion in the district in January-December 2022. 251.5 billion soums or 2.7% of the total volume of industrial products were produced by small business entities. Composition of industrial production (in billion soums). The interaction between the state and the private sector plays a major role in increasing the interest of private business in ensuring a stable socio-economic situation in the country. In turn, it can be seen that as a result of the reforms being carried out in our country in terms of expropriation and privatization, the share of the non-state sector in the volume of production of industrial products in the district is significant. 7045.6 bln. in January-December 2022 by network enterprises. Soum worth of products were produced.

Social and economic indicators of Tuproqkala district.	
Schools - 21 MTM - 44 units Libraries - 1 Health institutions - 11 Mosques - 5	New jobs - 13,800 Unemployment rate - 6.8% Those who went to work abroad - 4,500 Unemployed - 2.1 thousand people.
	Income to the local budget - 90.4 billion soums.
The level of natural gas supply is 99.4%.	The level of drinking water supply is 94.3%.
Large industrial enterprises - 4 (TUYAMOYIN HYDROELECTRICAL STATION UK, "UZAUTO MOTORS" Khorazm branch, KHORAZM SHAKAR LLC, "NEW BEST STYLE" LLC)	Joint ventures - 2. The number of foreign enterprises is 3 small industrial enterprises - 185. During the reporting period, the number of small business entities increased to 13.
The share of regional industry in district industry - 54.3% (11489.9 billion soums growth rate - 105.3%)	Share in service provision - 2.1%, (growth rate of 275.1 billion soums - 110.1%)
Capitalized investment funds - 514.5 billion soums.	<i>Including foreign investments and loans - 72.1 billion soums.</i>
Export volume - 15.9 million dollars. (completion - 178.5%) Import volume - 190.1 million dollars. (completion - 92.4%)	Including the export plan of industrial products - 14.2 million dollars. In practice - 15.9 million dollars. (128%) Fruit and vegetable products export plan - 7.2 million dollars. In practice - 7.6 thousand dollars. (1%)
191.0 million soums allocated from the support fund for farmers, peasant farms	Loans allocated on the basis of the program "Each family is an entrepreneur" -

and homestead land owners.	26.6 billion soums.
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Agricultural indicators.

Agricultural land - 160,000 ha, including irrigated land - 104,050 ha, cotton - 2,800 ha, grain - 1,500 ha, perennial trees - 465 ha, pastures - 100,789 ha, land o average credit rating - 47 points.

Cotton production - 10.1 thousand tons, compared to the plan - (450 tons) 104.7% was completed.	Cotton production - 10.1 thousand tons, compared to the plan - (450 tons) 104.7% was completed.
Livestock - 21.5 thousand heads. compared to 2022 - increased by 0.3 thousand heads (100.6%).	Livestock - 21.5 thousand heads. compared to 2022 - increased by 0.3 thousand heads (100.6%).

Today, growing high-quality food products in a natural way and providing employment to the population is becoming an urgent issue all over the world.

Now, in order to prevent the deterioration of the ecology and food shortage, and to provide employment to the population, these processes are actively continuing in our district, to develop land and increase productivity in agriculture, to provide employment to the population. Subsidies and large loans are allocated for agroclusters and farmers participating in the development of new lands, proposals and projects on fuel lubrication and water saving are regularly heard. This year, within the framework of the head of state's visit to Khorezm region, it is planned to develop 50,000 hectares of land in Tuproqkala district, and today 352 hectares have been developed. For the first time, 80 hectares of land were harvested and used for cultivation. 80 hectares of land were auctioned and presented to entrepreneurs.

It was decided to grow food and grain crops (rice, wheat) and fodder crops for livestock on these lands. For this purpose, new land clearing works were started in 7 objects in the district, and irrigation and reclamation networks were built. At present, in order to save water, concrete construction of canals and construction of drains is being carried out, and in order to prevent water hazards, works are being carried out to strengthen and concrete the dams of the Amudarya water basin. In addition, in order to protect nature, planting saxophone plants in the desert area, planting mulberries, grapes, apples and other fruit and ornamental plants on the edges of each contour in order to effectively use the edges of cultivated fields.

Summary. It was noted that a lot of attention is being paid to the youth of the district, and the pace of development has been accelerated in a short time. Various initiatives and programs to support young people, as well as the positive impact of these efforts on society, are showing their strength. The article also describes the main factors contributing to the impressive growth and development observed in the district. Overall, it is said to demonstrate the tremendous focus and investment in youth and the remarkable progress achieved in a short period of time. Such changes in the district in a short period of time, the new construction and modern equipment of schools and kindergartens, the bringing of qualified personnel with concern for the health of the population located 200 km from the center of the district, are creating great comfort for the residents of Amunkal.

A lot of opportunities are being created for small business and individual entrepreneurs, and in order to keep the population busy without leaving home, many sectors such as livestock breeding, poultry farming, fishing are being established. In order to ensure the employment of women, the district administration provides sewing machines free of charge to women on social protection, and to women entrepreneurs on the basis of interest-free loan subsidies. Such attention to the population is reflected in the fact that in the hearts of every person and the growing youth, love for the Motherland, young people who selflessly serve their profession are growing up.

Of course, we would like to express our gratitude to our head of state Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, who creates such opportunities and pays great attention to the residents of our district, including our youth.

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INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY